

[Google DeepMind introduces AlphaFold 3 AI model:](#) The new AI model, AlphaFold 3, accurately predicts the 3D folded structure of proteins based on their amino acid sequences. It also can predict the interaction of proteins with other molecules. The AlphaFold Serve has been made openly accessible by Google DeepMind, which is expected to help drive drug discovery breakthroughs by expediting the identification of new drug targets. DeepMind has yet to release the downloadable code of AlphaFold 3.

[GSK backs Fleming Initiative with £45m pledge to help fight against drug resistant infections:](#) GSK will be the first founding partner of the Fleming Initiative, which seeks to tackle anti-microbial resistance (AMR). This initiative is a new collaborative approach led by Imperial College Healthcare NHS Trust and Imperial College London. AMR is recognized by the World Health Organization as an urgent public health threat.

[Ionis and Biogen discontinue experimental ALS drug following failed Phase I/II study:](#) After failing to show any improvement among patients in a Phase I/II study, Ionis and Biogen are halting the development of their experimental treatment for amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS). The search for a new treatment for ALS also took a setback when Amylyx Pharmaceuticals axed Relyvrio, its ALS drug, from the market last month after their Phase III Phoenix trial failed to meet its endpoints.

[WHO Approves Vaccine for Dengue fever:](#) Takeda Pharmaceutical's dengue vaccine, QDENGGA (TAK-003), has been prequalified by the World Health Organization (WHO). This prequalification will provide international procurement, such as UNICEF, agencies with another option against the disease. It is estimated that last year there was 5 million cases and 5000 deaths due to the disease. The other available dengue vaccine is Dengvaxia by Sanofi. However, Dengvaxia is reported to have an elevated risk of severe disease in children who have no prior exposure to dengue.

[20,000 volunteers recruited for the Genes and Cognition Cohort within the National Institute for Health and Care Research \(NIHR\) BioResource:](#) The University of Cambridge and Alzheimer's Society have recruited more than 20,000 volunteers for the NIHR BioResource's Genes and Cognition Cohort. The resource is aimed at accelerating the development of drugs to treat dementia. For example, pharmaceutical companies with promising drug candidates to slow cognitive decline can recruit participants through the BioResource. Despite progress towards developing drugs to slow down the progression of dementia, current leading treatments have only a small effect.